

CULTURAL SCIENCES

HORA MORTULUI (HORA FOR THE DECEASED) - WAKE SONG FROM BIHOR COUNTY

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Abstract

In Bihor County, there is a *Hora mortului* (The Romanian term *hora* can be understood as *to sing in grief for the dead*), a generic title for two funeral popular literary creations, i.e. a wake song and another piece, simply called verse. The wake song *Hora mortului* is a ceremonial song performed at midnight, the evening before the wake, by both men and women. The song was sung in the room where the wake was held, around the coffin. The actors (people singing) were divided into two groups that sit on either side of the coffin, behind the family members. The atmosphere was sober, the elements of props are missing; the solemnity was given by the serious tone of the melody and the text. The compositional structure of the wake song and the melody were known to those performing in a community. From a compositional point of view, the studied texts do not differ much; an archetypal variant can be traced. Most of the pieces I have studied start with the reason for the trip/departure. Following this path, the literary motifs of the wake song summarize the essential elements of the funeral ceremony: like the deathbed, deceptive death, the cuckoo bird, the last journey, the cemetery, the grave or final separation from the loved ones. Relevant to *Hora mortului* is the motif of the cuckoo bird; the cuckoo, although at the feet of the dead, is not a messenger of death, but, on the contrary, the symbol of life. The bird becomes a dialogue partner for Death. Death is personified and asks the cuckoo, here a symbol of life, to change voices. Its refusal turns into a death sentence. Death appears as a sly, deceitful, and unjust female mythic representation. In the final part of the wake song, the dead, through the voices of those who interpret the song, says goodbye to everyone in the family; the wishes of the dead are also listed, so they could be imprinted in the memory of the loved ones. The verses that illustrate the departure of the dead from this world underline the resignation to the omnipresence of death.

Keywords: lament/wake lyrics, funeral ceremonial, Bihor County, cuckoo bird, deathbed, final separation/detarture from the loved ones.

In Romanian, the verb "a hori" has two meanings: to sing a song, usually a hora (by mouth or by whistle)¹ and "to play the hora".² In both meanings of the term we find the noun "hora" and the only difference is the relation to it. The Explanatory Dictionary of the Romanian Language attributes a Bulgarian etymology (from *horo*) to the word "horă", and explains it as "a Romanian folk dance with a gentle rhythm, in which performers hold hands, forming a closed circle; a circle formed by those who perform this dance; a melody to which this dance is performed".³

Ivan Evseev calls the hora "the most complex and widespread Romanian folk dance"⁴ which is found in all rites of passage, which also justifies the different perceptions among researchers. Romulus Vulcănescu attributes a solar, heliolatric nature to the hora, while Elena-Niculita Voronca attributes it a telluric character, dedicated to a chthonic deity, as every hora includes kicking the ground with one's feet.⁵ Regardless of the characteristics attributed to it, the hora is certainly a ceremonial "with a multifaceted symbolism."⁶

Hora as a dance is part of the rites of passage, "helping the performer move from one state to another, precisely due to its magical function."⁷ Delia Suiogan

reveals the "horal" character of the main rites of passage. As part of the birth rites, one plays a hora with the child after the latter is placed on the threshold and is lifted up by the mother, who places them in the father's arms. This hora is a form of honoring the child's birth and signifies the child's introduction into the magical, protective circle.⁸ In the nuptial ceremony, the horas are diversified, "the rites of consecration and initiation are doubled by the founding and the sacrificial rites".⁹ In the funeral ceremony, the passage of the immaculate wanderer from one world to another, "but above all the assurance of separation, are acts of a magic of the hora."¹⁰

In the funeral ceremony, we find the hora nature in several moments, some of which are obvious, such as the hora around the fire in the wake evening or the alms hora, while others are suggested by the numerous magic circles made around the coffin, around the house where the dead person lies, around the grave or the alms table. Delia Suiogan also attributes a hora character to the ride from the dead person's house to the cemetery, "whether we talk about a ride on the concentric circle

¹ <https://dexonline.ro>

² Ibid.

³ Ibid.

⁴ Ivan Evseev, *Enciclopedia simbolurilor religioase și arhetipale culturale*, Editura „Învieră”, 2007, p. 262.

⁵ Ibid.

⁶ Ibid.

⁷ Delia Suiogan, *Simbolistica riturilor de trecere*, Editura „Paideia”, București, 2006, p. 173.

⁸ Ibid.

⁹ Ibid.

¹⁰ Ibid.

system or the spiral one (the most common in traditional Romanian communities)".¹¹

Romulus Antonescu summarizes the hora instances of the Romanian funeral ceremony: the dance surrounding the grave, the alms-giving dance, the wake dance. The grave-circling dance is performed after the deceased has been buried, a girdle is performed around the grave, going round it in a circle, and it signifies the very end of the separation stage of the dead from the living and the full integration into the other world. In Valea Almăjului, this dance is only performed around the graves of the young, unmarried dead people and is part of the complex of representations of a dead person's marriage. In Banat and Oltenia, the alms-giving dance is played, an event which takes place during funeral ceremonies, when a girdle or a hora is performed "for their soul's sake". They dance in a circle, men and women are holding hands with lit candles and flowers being offered by the family of the deceased. The dance is based on the belief that the remembered dead persons return and attend the party themselves, rejoicing with the crowd, so it is a bridge between the two worlds, if not a process of recalling them so that they can see how much affection the living have for them. In Vrancea, one knows the wake dance (Chiperiul), a male dance with specially-made masks. The dance takes place in the courtyard around a fire, and the dancers group themselves in a row, one behind the other, each holding the predecessor's girdle. The leader holds a lit stick or pole. The purpose of the dance is to trick those in line into falling into the fire. Funeral masks used to embody the deceased in old times, the one who dresses in this way representing the ancestor, thus updating communication with the deceased and gaining their goodwill. At the same time, it is also a tool meant to frighten the dead away from harming people, or to drive away other evil spirits which are particularly active in the passing period, so that they do not harm either the recently dead or those gathered around their body.¹²

In the area under study, the Beiuș Basin, the term "hora" is used in funeral ceremonies to mean, in particular, "song", the *Hora mortului* (*Hora for the Deceased*) being the generic title for funerary texts. In the research area, it is under this name of *Hora mortului* that we found two popular creations which are different both in terms of content and the moment in which they were performed: ceremonial song and lament.

A first song called *Hora mortului* (*Hora for the Deceased*) is a ceremonial song, performed at the wake in the evening before the funeral. As midnight approached, a wake participant would announce to those present that twelve o'clock was approaching. "At midnight, while people sit by the body, a more skilled woman sang *Hora mortului* (*Hora for the Deceased*). In Budureasa, Manea Firoanda was specialized in

this"¹³. The family would gather around the coffin, sit on either side of the coffin and listen devoutly to *Hora mortului* (*Hora for the Deceased*). The moment used to be very powerful. The participants in the wake approached the room where the coffin was laid, those who knew how to sing *Hora mortului* (*Hora for the Deceased*) entered the house, the others found a place as close as possible, with priority given to family and close relatives. While lament is an exclusively female attribute, in the villages of the Beiuș Basin, *Hora mortului* (*Hora for the Deceased*) was sung by both men and women: "unlike other funeral songs performed only by women, men can also join in the wake songs"¹⁴. The performance of a wake song requires, as with any mourning event, that certain expression and behavior patterns be respected. The song was performed in the room where the deceased was laid to rest, around the coffin. The performers were divided into two groups who sat on either side of the coffin, behind the family members. The time chosen for performing this wake song is not by chance - twelve o'clock on the last night of the wake. Thus, the funeral ceremonial events of the two wake nights are hierarchical, the most important of which seems to have been the last night of the wake. The ritual songs are rigorously correlated with certain moments of the funeral ceremony. The timing of their performance is explained by the specificity of the day and night time schedule in the traditional village. The reference points of this schedule, established according to the diurnal course of the sun, are: morning, opposite to evening, and noon, opposite to midnight.¹⁵ The time chosen for performing the wake song, *Hora mortului* (*Hora for the Deceased*), can be explained through the belief that the most dangerous time, both for the community and for the deceased, is the night, especially midnight, when they are still in the house, and as it is forbidden to lament at night, the wake song is performed. In addition, "at the beginning of each time segment, the journey of the dead person's soul encounters difficulties that cannot be overcome by the ritual song alone, which is intended to set it back on the unique path of integration into the other world."¹⁶

Placing the performers around the coffin supports the hora nature of this wake song. The atmosphere is sober, "a sober line dominates in the wake song, restrained even in moments of maximum pain intensity expressed by the text",¹⁷ props elements are missing, while the serious tone of the melody and the text would generate solemnity. "From a musical point of view, the wake song from Bihor County adheres to melodies related to the *doina*, with free form and slow movement. Through simple forms and archaic rhythms, it gives a vibrant color. With little sound material, it achieves great effects."¹⁸

¹¹ Ibid., p. 174.

¹² Antonescu Romulus, Dicționar de simboluri și credințe tradiționale românești, 2009, Ediția digitală, 2016, pp. 203-204.

¹³ Ion Ghinoiu, Cartea românească a morților. De la veacul de om la veacul vecilor, Editura „Univers Enciclopedic Gold”, București, 2019, pp. 192-193.

¹⁴ Ibid., p. 193.

¹⁵ Ernest Bernea, Cadre ale gândirii populare românești, Cartea românească, București, 1985, pp. 303-306.

¹⁶ Gheorghe Enache, Călătoria cu roua-n picioare, cu ceața-n spinare, Editura Paideia, București, 2006, p. 270.

¹⁷ Ion Bradu, Cântecele și jocul de priveghi, în „Zilele folclorului bihorean”, Oradea, 1968, p. 139.

¹⁸ Ibid.

After performing this song, the performers are rewarded, a family member or relative stands by the door with a bottle of brandy and some bread as alms. Each man drank from that bottle, saying "May God forgive them", while the bread and drink symbolised a first alms meal given for honouring the soul of the deceased. The reward is therefore also part of the act of facilitating the soul's easier integration into the Afterlife. At this time most of the participants in the wake used to go home, leaving only family members, close relatives and men playing cards.

Today, in the villages surveyed, this wake song is no longer sung. We have collected alternative songs from those who, until fifteen to twenty years ago, were still adapting and performing *Hora mortului* (*Hora for the Deceased*). Our interviewees regret the loss of this custom, which they considered important both for the deceased and for the whole community. The disappearance of this custom is associated by these people with the desacralization of the moment and with the loss of the new generation's respect for their ancestors.

We will now try to analyse the meanings of this wake song using texts from literature and texts collected from our interviewees. The compositional structure of the wake song and the melody were known to those who used to perform in a community. From a compositional point of view, the studied texts do not differ much, and an archetypal variant can be traced.

Most of the variants consulted begin with the journey motif, a hypothetical journey: „Off did I go / Through the garden of the Greeks (meaning Orthodox, here) / By the shade of walnut trees”¹⁹ or „Off did I go / By the garden of the Greeks, / By the leaf of the peach-trees.”²⁰ The journey motif at the beginning of the text must be correlated with the ancient myth of the great passage, a myth found in a wonderful poetic achievement in *Cântecul zorilor* (*The Song of Dawn*). The elements of the great passage myth are found in the *Hora mortului* (*Hora for the Deceased*) and in the following moments, where the deceased prepares for the journey and asks his wife: „Thou, wife, please bring a pot of wine / As I leave and won't come back. / Thou, wife, please bring a pot of water / As I'll go straight to the grave.”²¹

The version taken from Pocola begins in a stylistic manner, with the mist motif, a recurring motif in the songs from Beiuș Basin: „Lord, has it misted over / Up by the foot of the mountain / At the eaves of the pine tree.”²² The mist here becomes a metaphor for death, keeping the analogy with the vegetable world, once the mist has fallen over, nature dies. The myth of the hypothetical journey must be related to the unpredictability of the time of death. The explanation is supported by

the verse found in some versions: „But what did I just find over there”²³ or But what did I just find in the garden.”²⁴

From this part, the literary motifs of the wake song summarise the essential elements of the funeral ceremony: the motif of the dead person's bed, the deceitful death motif, the cuckoo motif, the final journey motif, the cemetery motif, the grave motif, the farewell motif.

The first part of the song develops the motif of the deathbed:

„A white crib wrapped in white pine planks / But what's in the crib? / Green grass from the field. / Who mowed the grass? / It's a whole string of nuts. / Who did the weeding? / His sister along with his mother. / Grass is covered in a white cloth (thick, woollen fabric, usually white). / Cloth is covered with a pillow. / Providing (the name of the dead man) John some well-deserved rest.”²⁵ or A pretty pine crib; / But what's in the crib? / Green grass from the field. / Who mowed the grass? / His brother and his father. / Who did the weeding? / His sister and his mother.”²⁶ or From a nicely-plumped crib / Made of white pine tree planks. / But what's in the crib? / Flowers in the field. / Green grass in the field. / Grass is covered in a white cloth, / Cloth is covered with a pillow. Providing Todora (the name of the dead man) some well-deserved rest.”²⁷

The deathbed motif brings the moment of preparing the coffin to the fore, an important detail of the funeral ceremony. The wood used to make the coffin is from pine trees and the coffin is decorated with grass and flowers. We also notice the involvement of the family in getting the coffin ready. The *haba*, which refers here to the *lipideu*, which is sometimes woven specifically for the coffin, placed under the dead body, and the *pillow* are also mentioned. There is obvious care for the righteous preparation of the coffin, which will become the place of *hodină* (final rest). In the villages of Beiuș Basin, as soon as someone died, the village craftsman was called in to make the coffin: "there were some skilled carpenters in the village, who made coffin caskets"²⁸, "they bring in pine tree planks and some master craftsman makes the coffin, which is usually only polished and left uncoloured"²⁹. Most of the time the family had the wooden material for the coffin in the attic. Usually, the wood used to make the coffin was from pine tree, but also beech, and it is customary to place the remains of the used planks (sawdust and splinters) on the bottom of the coffin, along with other bedding, "*talaș* was placed on the bottom of the coffin, made from the planks from which the coffin was made. The pillow under the dead person's head was also filled with *talaș*. A white lace sheet (*lipideu*) was placed over

¹⁹ Mariana Kahane, Lucilia Georgescu-Stănculeanu, *Cântecul Zorilor și Bradului*, Editura Muzicală, București, 1988, p. 654.

²⁰ Informant Maria Straca, Petrani, 43 years old.

²¹ Ion Gh. Roman, *Jocurile de priveghi din Bihor* (Valea Crișului Negru, de la Beiuș la Tinca) „Crisia”, XVII, Oradea, 1987, p. 498.

²² Informant Dumitru Serb, Pocola, 87 years old.

²³ Mariana Kahane, Lucilia Georgescu-Stănculeanu, *Cântecul Zorilor...*, op.cit., p. 654.

²⁴ Ion Gh. Roman, *Jocurile de priveghi...*, op.cit., p. 497.

²⁵ Ibid., p. 498.

²⁶ Ion Bradu, *Cântecul și jocul...*, op.cit., p. 136.

²⁷ Mariana Kahane, Lucilia Georgescu-Stănculeanu, *Cântecul Zorilor...*, op.cit., p. 654.

²⁸ Alexandru Popa, *Povestea satului din Țara Beiușului*. Lazuri de Beiuș, Editura „Primus”, Oradea, 2016, p. 82.

²⁹ Moise Popovici, *Monografia comunei Seghiște, „Transilvania”, nr. 3, Sibiu, 1911, p. 227.*

the *talaș*, and a white towel (*felegă*) was put over the crossed hands of the deceased³⁰.

What is recurring in this first part of the wake song is the epithet white (*dalb*): „A white crib wrapped / with white pine planks” or „Grass is covered with a white cloth” (thick, woollen fabric, usually white). The epithet can be related to the metaphor of the *dalb de pribeag*, which Mihai Pop explains as “a metaphor used in most ceremonial songs, it recalls the old metaphors based on verbal prohibition, a taboo. In the traditional view, it springs from the idea that death is a great journey from the world of the living to the world of the dead. In folk dialect, a “*pribeag*” is one who has left his home and his loved ones and wanders the world. The flowers in the carols choruses are “*dalbe*”, as is the bride-to-be in the carol: “The immaculate girl has given / Him, the young groom, commands”, dreams are also “*dalbe*”, as is the young man. The epithet, with its particular sound given by the age and rarity of the term, is of particular gentleness.”³¹ The recurring epithet in *Hora mortului* (*Hora for the Deceased*) reveals, first of all, the sacredness of the instance in the funeral ceremony, the coffin preparation, which is to be home for the passage from this world, according to the view of inhabitants in the researched villages, the coffin/mortuary is a new home: “My baby, I don't like your home / As it has no doors or shutters.”³² In this sense, Mihai Pop points out: “*Dalb* is a word with symbolic value in the folk poetry arsenal” and “the sense of purity is defining for this word deriving from *white*.”³³

What is also relevant is the diminutive *pătuț* (crib), which, in some variants, receives the epithet *mândru* (pretty): *A white crib wrapped*³⁴ or *A pretty pine crib*.³⁵ The diminutive can be associated with the simplicity of the coffin, but it can also express the affection, the emotion that strikes a person when parting from their loved ones, while the epithet *mândru* (pretty) is to be understood here as garnished with all that is necessary for the deceased.

The funerary text continues with the deceitful death motif:

„But who's lying in bed? / Did Ioane get drunk? / He drank from a glass, / The glass was poisoned / And he didn't wake up anymore. / How do you catch him drinking / With no one to talk to / But who sits by his body? / Death sits, you ranger / Who tied his tongue.³⁶ or But who's lying in bed / Did Teodora get drunk? / Who got drunk? / Or is death in a hurry? / Who tied his tongue?³⁷ or But who's lying in bed? / Miroane (here we say the name of the dead man) is dead drunk. / But he's not drunk from drinking / But because of a spell. / But who got him under a spell? / As death got a hold of

him / She's sitting by his body (poor her).³⁸ or But who's sitting by his body? / It's the grotesque death, / Who tied his tongue.”³⁹

This section of the song is made up of several rhetorical questions. The lyrics are also relevant to how one views the moment when death occurs: death, which is personified here, comes suddenly, the man, who can no longer speak, seems to be drunk or under a spell. In the version taken from Petrani, there is a time that also gives the motif of resisting death, and this increases the drama of the moment: *And it kept constraining him / Until he drank it all*.⁴⁰

Also relevant to the *Hora mortului* (*Hora for the Deceased*) is the cuckoo motif: „Who sits by his feet / It's the grieving cuckoo”⁴¹ or „By his holy feet / Sits the grieving cuckoo”⁴² or „Who sits by his feet? / It's the miserable cuckoo.”⁴³ Here, the cuckoo, although sitting by the feet of the deceased, is not a death messenger, as we find it in other parts of the country, when it sings to the left of the man, behind his back or near his house,⁴⁴ but, on the contrary, it is the symbol of life. The cuckoo does not have the functions and values of a psychopomp animal, it takes part in a dialogue “that is meant to confirm the gap between the living and the dead, between those who stay close to home and those who have left on the road of no return”.⁴⁵ The epithet *jelnicule/jalnicu* (grieving, poor) here means being overcome with grief, helpless, “in songs about death, the cuckoo, as mediator between worlds, carries news from one realm to another, but does not allow the protagonist to cross the specific customs of this journey.”⁴⁶

The cuckoo becomes a dialogue partner for death: „And death speaks to them / Hey, cuckoo, you griever, / Let's exchange voices! / And the cuckoo spoke: / I will not exchange my voice / With anyone in this world/ For you, death, with your voice / You only bring trouble into the world. / You separate husband from wife, / You separate a child from the mother/ And you loose maiden girls / And you make many homes desolate. / I, death, with my voice / Come spring time / I'll go out in the field / And I'll sit on a green branch / And I'll sing my mourning out to the world. / I'll be listened to / By the ploughmen with their ploughs / The cowboys with their cows / The shepherds with their sheep / The wives with their cloths / The girls with their baskets / The old ladies with their cloth.”⁴⁷ or And death speaks to them / - Hey, cuckoo, you poor thing, / Let's exchange voices. / But the cuckoo spoke: / - No, I will not exchange / As you, with your little voice, / You separate husband from wife / Sons from mothers / When spring comes, I'll go out in the woods. / I'll sit on a green branch / And from there I'll just sing / And I'll

³⁰ Butișcă Constantin, *Satul Sudrigiu. Case, oameni și tradiții*, Editura „Brevis”, Oradea, 2016, p. 275.

³¹ *Ibid.*, p. 186.

³² *Ibid.*, p. 32.

³³ Mihai Pop, *Mitul marii treceri*, „Folclor literar”, vol. II, Timișoara, 1968, p. 79.

³⁴ Ion Gh. Roman, *Jocurile de priveghi...*, op.cit., p. 498.

³⁵ Ion Bradu, *Cântecul și jocul...*, op.cit., p. 136.

³⁶ Ion Gh. Roman, *Jocurile de priveghi...*, op.cit., p. 498.

³⁷ *Ibid.*

³⁸ Informant Dumitru Serb, Pocola, 87 years old.

³⁹ Ion Bradu, *Cântecul și jocul...*, op.cit., p. 137.

⁴⁰ Informant Maria Straca, Petrani, 43 years old.

⁴¹ Ion Gh. Roman, *Jocurile de priveghi...*, op.cit., p. 498.

⁴² Mariana Kahane, Lucilia Georgescu-Stănculeanu, *Cântecul Zorilor...*, op.cit., p. 655.

⁴³ Informant Dumitru Serb, Pocola, 87 years old.

⁴⁴ Ivan Evseev, *Enciclopedia...* op.cit., p. 156.

⁴⁵ Mihai Coman, *Bestiarul mitologic românesc*, Editura Fundației Culturale Române, București, 1996, p. 123.

⁴⁶ *Ibid.*, p. 124.

⁴⁷ Ion Gh. Roman, *Jocurile de priveghi...* op.cit., p. 498.

sing with so much grief / That rivers will stop flowing,
/ And I'll sing with such longing / That the oxen will
stop moving in the field / They will all listen to me /
The cowboys will / The shepherds will.⁴⁸ or And death
speaks to them / Hey, cuckoo, you griever, / Let's ex-
change voices. / Hey, death, I will not exchange. / Your
voice, death, brings no good. / As your voice brings
trouble, / You separate husband from wife / Leaving
poor orphans behind / You separate children from par-
ents / As well as siblings / Hey, death, my voice is better
/ Come spring time / When herds wander outside / The
shepherd with his sheep, / But also pigs / They will all
listen to my voice.⁴⁹

Death is personified and asks the cuckoo, a symbol
of life here, to exchange voices. The cuckoo's refusal is
a condemnation of death. Death appears as a cunning,
deceitful and unjust female mythical representation:

„For you, death, with your voice / You only bring
trouble into the world. / You separate husband from
wife, / You separate a child from the mother/ And you
loose maiden girls / And you make many homes deso-
late.”⁵⁰

The artistic representations of heaven and hell are
also unique:

„I saw the beautiful heaven / Like the shining sun,
/ I saw tables all spread out / And wax lamps being lit⁵¹
or The angel of death now / Accompanies him on his
way / And takes him to hell / Where all sinners burn.”⁵²

Heaven is associated with the sun and, therefore,
with light, while hell is perceived as a place of torment,
where sinners' souls burn. The verse "I saw tables all
spread out" completes the image of heaven and makes
it real; the *spread out table* becomes an occasion and a
place for meeting the ancestors.

Starting with this moment, the song changes com-
pletely, in the sense that the performers borrow the dead
person's voice, as they are preparing for the great fare-
well. In some versions, this final scene is more devel-
oped and includes the motif of the journey to the cem-
etry:

„On a long stretch of hilly land / A pretty chariot
is always loaded / With only priests and people. / But
Ioane asks them: / Where are you going, folks?! - We
are going to the cemetery, / To share the graves. / But
Ioane asked them: / - Take me away / While I'm with
you / And I'll hold you with my arm.”⁵³

followed by the separation motif:

„But Ioane asks them: - Give me, wife, a pot of
water, / For tomorrow I'll go straight to the grave; /
Give me, wife, a pot of wine, / For I go and come no
more. / I'll go to the green meadow, / No one in the
world will see me. / I'll go into the dry ground / Today,
tomorrow, I'll be forgotten.”⁵⁴

In some versions, the scene goes straight to the de-
ceased saying goodbye to everyone in the house
through the voices of those singing the wake song:

„Give me, wife, a pot of wine / For I go and come
no more. / Give me, wife, a pot of water / For I go
straight to the grave. / As even for royal courts / When
death comes, you leave all behind. / As even for golden
courts / When death comes, you leave them all.”⁵⁵

The verses illustrating the parting of the dead from
those in this world illustrate resignation in the face of
death's omnipresence. The verses in the analysed vari-
ants conclude that the dead only need a pot of wine and
a pot of water for the great journey. The concept of
wine "being considered, from ancient times, a sacred
beverage",⁵⁶ was taken up by Christianity, thus wine
was accepted as a eucharistic substance, representing
the holy blood of Christ, "thus including the meanings
of immortality and resurrection from the world of the
dead".⁵⁷ Water is always present in the funeral cere-
mony, being loaded with symbolism, "water, the fun-
eral ritual operator, can have both positive and nega-
tive representations."⁵⁸ In *Hora mortului (Hora for the
Deceased)*, water is a positive symbol, being a vital
source to be correlated with the belief in the Afterlife.
Both wine and water here prefigure the alms meal that
will be given in honour of the dead person's soul.

In the version taken from Petrani, the seg-
ment where the dead person says goodbye is more devel-
oped, the last wishes of the dead are listed, through
which they try to stay alive in the memory of their loved
ones:

„Then the deceased would come back / Asking the
wife or husband: / Bring me (name) a pot of water / For
I go straight to the grave/ Bring me (name) a pot of wine
/ For I go and come no more. / And (name of the dead
person) would come back / And to (name of wife/hus-
band) would ask / To keep writing it, keep writing it /
On the corner of the table / When they would eat on the
table / To remember them / May God rest their soul! /
And (the dead man's name) would come back / And
asked (the husband's wife's name) / She kept writing it,
writing it / On the spoon's handle / When she ate with
the spoon / To remember him / May God rest their soul!
/ Again (the dead man's name) she turned / And prayed
for (the husband's wife's name) / To keep writing it,
keep writing it / When they slept on the pillow / To re-
member them / May God rest their soul! / And (the dead
man's name) would come back / And asked their chil-
dren / The wind blows in the plum trees / Farewell, my
little ones / The wind blows through the vineyard /
Farewell, dear husband or wife / The wind blows
through the flowers / Farewell, brothers and sisters /
The wind blows through the feathers / Farewell, my fel-
low villagers/ For I'm leaving you all / And come back
no more.”⁵⁹

⁴⁸ Mariana Kahane, Lucilia Georgescu-Stănculeanu, *Cântecul Zorilor...*, op.cit., p. 655.

⁴⁹ Informant Dumitru Serb, Pocola, 87 years old.

⁵⁰ Ion Gh. Roman, *Jocurile de priveghi...*, op.cit., p. 478.

⁵¹ Informant Maria Straca, Petrani, 43 years old.

⁵² Ibid.

⁵³ Ion Gh. Roman, *Jocurile de priveghi...*, op.cit., p. 498.

⁵⁴ Ibid.

⁵⁵ Mariana Kahane, Lucilia Georgescu-Stănculeanu, *Cântecul Zorilor ...*, op.cit., p. 655.

⁵⁶ Ofelia Văduva, *Pași spre sacru. Din etnologia alimentației românești*, Editura Etnologică, București, 2011, p.45.

⁵⁷ Ibid, p.46.

⁵⁸ Nicolae Panea, *Gramatica funerarului*, Editura „Scrisul Românesc”, Craiova, 2003, p. 115.

⁵⁹ Informant Maria Straca, Petrani, 43 years old.

In the version I collected from Pocola, *Hora mortului (Hora for the Deceased)* ends with the giving thanks motif:

„We thank the Holy Father / For he gave the leaf to the Earth. / We thank St. George for giving the leaf to the forest. / We thank the Holy Easter / For giving the green leaf to the beeches. / We thank the Father again / For getting us through to spring.”⁶⁰

The thanks addressed to God or to the saints reveal the optimism of the people in the villages of Beiuș Basin, who, through these verses, testify that their lives are in God's hands and that the death of a community member can be overcome with God's help. This version taken from Pocola also has a chorus: "May God forgive him" or "May God forgive her", which is sung after a group of verses, three, four or five verses, according to the choice of the performers. The forgiveness motif also appears in the version from the village of Sititelec - *Hora mortului (Hora for the Deceased)* ends with the verse *May Holy God forgive them!*⁶¹

In the version from Beiușele and Pociovești, the wake song contains a lyrical scene of eight verses that increase the drama of the moment through the motif of the time of death and support the myth of the great passage through the motif of the road of no return:

„You, mountains, pour some rain, and shake / You all chant powerfully, / His sad journey. / - I would not come, but I have no choice, / For even death does not leave me alone. / It came over with a command / My soul to carry / Into God's hand / For it's from there that I've received it myself.”⁶²

Through hyperbolization, the lyrics emphasise the pain caused by the separation of the dead from this world and express the idea that the human soul belongs to God, while death is seen as the soul's return to its creator.

The version from Beiușele and Pociovești is also unique in ten other verses:

„And the walnut leaf fell, / The father leaves his children behind. / And he said he would come again / When walnuts blossom, / As he misses his children. / And he said he would come again / When beans blossom, / As he misses his wife; / When flowers blossom, / As he misses his neighbours.”⁶³

These lines develop the longing motif, a feeling which makes one who is forced to part from the loved ones promise to return.

In conclusion, the hora nature of the funeral ceremony in the researched area is supported both by the wake song *Hora mortului (Hora for the Deceased)* and by the multiple gestures of the ceremony. The *Hora mortului (Hora for the Deceased)* wake song performs complex functions within the funeral ceremony aimed at the separation, passage and integration of the dead, all carried out simultaneously.

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⁶⁰ Informant Dumitru Serb, Pocola, 87 years old.

⁶¹ Mariana Kahane, Lucilia Georgescu-Stănculeanu, *Cântecul Zorilor...*, op.cit., p. 656.

⁶² Ion Gh. Roman, *Jocurile de priveghi ...*, op.cit., p. 498.

⁶³ Ibid.